
THE RESTRUCTURING OF SCHOOL DISCIPLINE PATTERN IN NIGERIA EDUCATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Discipline is a way of ensuring compliance to rules, regulation and standard set by someone in the authority. This paper deals with the restructuring of school discipline pattern in Nigeria education system, which has been associated with child development discipline, school tradition, educational norm among others. Several disciplinary models such as Kounins model center assertive behavioural model and others were reviewed. Teachers can handle student misbehavior and maintain best practices through discipline in classrooms. The paper concluded that restructuring of school discipline encourage students to participate more in academic activities. The school administrators have essential roles to play in controlling discipline issues in schools.

Keywords: School, Discipline, Students, Administrator

Introduction

School remains a ground to empower and certify the requirement for human development and Nation up keeping. School is a type of service organization vested with primary function of educating the child and controlling their problems. School management has power and authority to control the conduct of students' activities through reasonable rules and regulations. These rules and regulations may, for example, define the expected standards of clothing, timekeeping, social behavior and work ethic (Olatunji, 2024). Rule and regulations must be enforced by members of staff or effective discipline to take place and to enable the student achieve the three domains of education namely: cognitive, effective and psychomotor domain.

Discipline is the act of instructing a person to follow a particular code of conduct that usually governs the organization. According to Ihendinihu (2024), discipline is the systematic practice of self-control in order to adhere to principles, values or established rules. The author added that it is the ability of a person to regulate his or her thoughts, emotions and actions in order to maintain order, and foster personal growth. It involves the enforcement of order to ensure that instruction is carried out. School discipline is described by Nnorom, Okonkwo, Ezeanolue and Nwankwo (2020) as the regulation of children and the maintenance of orders (rules) in schools. Discipline is the means of controlling the conduct of individuals in an organization. According to Atandaa and Wambugub (2022), discipline is a conscious effort geared towards training and developing people's character to follow an instituted order or an ethical standard

Discipline is the act of behaving in accordance with set law and regulations. Simatwa (2012) noted that discipline is not only training of the mind, but also exercising self-control and confidence to produce an orderly behaviour or character in an individual. It is the exhibition of good conduct in learning environment. Giwa and Yusoff (2024) maintained that discipline in school administration means abiding by school rules and regulations in a well-mannered, obedient, supportive and respective way. The authors added that discipline in school settings help to produce well-behaved students who do not only respect themselves but also the school authorities and regulations of the school.

In the field of child development, discipline refers to methods of modeling characters and of teaching self-control and acceptable behaviour. The aim of discipline is to set limits, restrict certain behaviours or attitudes that are harmful or against school policies, educational norms school tradition among others (Olatunji, 2024). Discipline helps children learn to control their behaviours, so that they act according to their ideas of what is right and wrong, not because of the fear of punishment. Although, punishment is seen as a disciplinary measure of a consequence of violating set-out rules. The school administrator used punishment to dismiss behaviours and deter other through the use of painful and unpleasant methods to control the students school administrators used two types of disciplinary measures to control the standard of schools' behavior in school setting.

Physical punishment physical or corporal punishment refers to intentional application of physical pain as a method of changing behavior. It includes a wide variety of methods such as hitting, slapping, choking, used of various objects/wooden paddles belts, stick/cane etc. Painful body postures (as placing in closed space) use of electric shock, use of excessive exercise drills of prevention from urine or stool elimination. The administration of physical punishment that entails physical chastisement needs to be done with caution. Corporal punishment must not be inflicted in such a way or with such force as may be considered

sadistic, cruel or excessive. Inatimi, Etigbamo and Egberibine (2024) pointed out that corporal punishment in schools occurs when the teacher or the "adult-in-charge" purposely inflicts pain upon a child in order to stop that child's unacceptable behaviour and/or inappropriate language. Continuing, Inatimi et al (2024) stressed that in corporal punishment, the adult usually hits various parts of the child's body with a hand, or with canes, paddles, yardsticks, belts, or other objects expected to cause pain and fear. The desirability and effectiveness of corporal punishment has seen as an anguish to human existed in the modern way of life. In the recent education reform of the world, especially in the development nation of the continent such as America, Europe and others while some parents, teachers, school administrators and general public have criticized corporal punishment in the school system, other are strongly opposed not to be used in school again. Corporal punishment is effective because, it makes students to think twice before committing the same offence, but very degenerously to students' psychological development on the school environment. The used of physical punishment can be deterrent to other students who might violate a rule in the absence of school staffs.

The modern school administrator opposed corporal punishment based on the following reason. It is cruel and inhuman. It holds considerable potential for child abuse. But physical punishment cannot be total avoided as a disciplinary measure in public school setting in Nigeria, based on the education development/standard of the country. Disciplinary problem dominates the issues of the day-to-day activities of school administrator, both large and small school or rural and urban settlement schools. Students disobey school rules and regulations with impurity, because of adolescent age of the students. They have little or no respect to their teachers and even the school Administrator. Base on that today, there is a slogan going on in the country today that education is scam, which is an act of indiscipline on the sight of students.

The alternative non-violent punishment includes soft verbal extinction distraction with holding measure and reward behavior modification. Instead of curbing behavior can aggravate it. Although, it has been emphasized that school authorities have the right to punish students for breach of school rules and regulation.

Student misbehaviour is a prevailing problem affecting schools not only in Nigeria but also across the global world. Ikegbusi and Manafa (2023) asserted that some students may display disruptive or problematic behavior in the classroom or school environment. Idoko (2021) noted that these disruptive or problematic behaviour include noise making in class, lateness to school, hatred for teachers, distracting others, interrupting the teacher, drinking alcohol, being domineering, pushing, fighting others, bullying, use of hand set in class, lack of interest, stealing, engaging in subject other than the one being discussed, attention seeking, staying outside the class as lessons go on, sleeping in class, and malpractices in assessments. Idoko added that others include truancy, immorality, indecent dressing, use of drugs, cultism and challenging constituted authority. Students misconduct occur everywhere in the world school administrator pay special interest in handling disciplinary issues, especially students misconduct in the classroom. Interferes with teaching and learning, and is through to be precursor and later school dropped and similar negative social outcomes. It also leads to teacher stress and attrition.

Discipline Motels

There are several model of taught that explain different ways of handling students discipline in school settings,

1. Kounin's Model

Kounin's (1976) is also a pioneer of a behaviour approach based on the typical behaviourist stimulus response theory. Kounin, like Skinner argues that learners will adopt good behaviour and eliminate bad behaviour in an attempt to gain the reward and avoid punishment. Kounin (1976) focus more on the behaviour of the educator and what the educator should be doing to achieve the desirable behaviour in learners. The school discipline model developed by Kounin (1976) is based on a detailed scientific analysis of school discipline and describes lesson and movement management as a means to control students' behaviour. The model could be termed a group dynamic model within which educators work with a group of learners.

Wiekkiewicz (1995), indicate that behaviour followed by undesirable incident, such as pain or fear, the behaviour is less likely to be repeated. Skinner focused on how the behaviour of the learner could be controlled and behaviour modification could be achieved for better understanding of teaching and learning for society improvement. Kounin recommends two techniques that can be used to address learner misbehaviour. He terms these i.e. "witnessing and overlapping". He described witnessing as the educator's attribute of having, "eyes at the back of their head" (Kounin 1976, 74).

The concept in its simplest terms implies that an educator must be able to know and see what is happening in his/her class, even if he/she is busy writing something to the learner on the chalkboard. An educator who is "with-it" knows what is going on in the classroom at all times (Burden 1995:47) overlapping is the ability to attend to two things at the same time, (Kounin 1976,85) for instance, an educator may be helping a small group of learners and simultaneously also observes the two other learners are playing instead of doing their class work or pay attention to their teacher, who is impacting knowledge to them.

2. Center Assertive Behavioral Model

Center and Center (1992) developed an approach which he terms "assertive discipline" that cannot be described as purely behaviorist in nature, but does contain certain elements of a behaviourist approach. Assertive discipline is different from many other models it provides a system of dealing with behaviour at the time it occurs, through a plan that make the learners responsible for his or her behaviour and resulting consequences (Steere 1978.46).

The importance of assertive discipline is captured in the following quotation: "An assertive educator will actively respond to a child's inappropriate behavior by clearly communicating to the child her disapproval of the behavior, followed by what he/she wants the child to do" (Duke and Meckel 1980). Key demand of assertive discipline mode is that students have right and that they need a caring educator who will provide warmth attention and support. Educators also have a right. They must teach in an environment that is conducive to learning and enjoy support from both parents and learners. Educator must be assertive and communicate to learner freely; they should also provide a model of good behavior. Students have the right to an educator who will be firm, consistent, provide positive encouragement and motivate good behavior in center and center.

Educator should also refrain from asking rhetorical questions about misbehavior and should develop a system from rewarding good behavior (Steer 1988, 48). The technique is very simple with the discipline. It puts the teacher in charge and makes him or her "the boss" of the classroom it does not use intimidation, threats, sarcasm or authoritarianism to get

results. It has no room for negatively disruptive behavior, bullying or ostracizing of other students. The basic principles of Center assertive behavioral model are catch students being good, make the rules very clear, do not be ambiguous, reward exceptional behavior, consistently let students know you are happy with good behavior and follow through with negative consequence for breaking the rules.

3. Cognitivist

This is a psychological approach which utilized overt behavior as a clue for deducing what goes on in the mind (Gage and Berliner 1992, 225). Cognitivist try to comprehend the kind of thinking associated with the particular content to be learned. They make a serious attempt to determine what goes on in the minds of learners, so that they do mathematics, read or understand instructions (Gage and Berliner 1992, 225 – 228).

Cognitivist Scientists in the field of education study the problems that require different kind of student's cognition. They maintain that if we understand how successful/unsuccessful learners think in better ways. Cognitivists place special emphasis on the think process of the learner. Pioneer in the field are the Gestalt psychologist, Kohler and Werthimer. Kohler studied the problem solving behavior of chimpanzees. He avoided detours and used tools such as sticks and boxes to achieve a remote goal. This processes of discovering a single and continuous solution even if it requires moving away from a goal to get a necessary goal to achieve a goal called insight. (Buckman 1992 – 42)

4. Psychologist

A psychologist from a behaviorist orientation study human behavior. In an attempt to understand the process, that will induce change in human behavior. The two prominent scholars in the field of behaviorist theory are Pavlor and Thorndike. In Pavlor's Classical Conditioning Model, dogs were conditioned to salivate at the sound of a time. (Conditioned Stimulus).When the tone was paired with food (Unconditioned Stimulus). Salivation was initially elicited as the unconditioned response to the food and came to be the sound of the tone alone.

Pavlor also experimented with secondary conditioning, generalization and discrimination. Thorndike on the other hand demonstrated that in both humans and animal a connection can be made between specific behaviors (or response) and the situation (or stimulus) if the result of such behavior is experienced as satisfying. He called this phenomenon the "Law of Effect".

5. William Glasser's Theories

It develops three theories on education called choice theory, quality management and reality therapy theory (Palmatier 1998, 3-33). Choice theory can be described as biological theory about our functioning as living creatures. The theory states that all behavior is an attempt by individual to satisfy needs that are built into the genetic structure of the brain. All motivation is internal not external meaning that motivation is directed from the brain which makes it cognitive in nature.

It stated that there is a special place on the brain where we measure and weight the outside data and reference their pieces of information with the mental pictures of our current wants to see it we have a sensory match.

Quality management is another of Glasser's Model that comprise his educational transformation theory. In order to manage people successfully, on must persuade them to put

what you want (i.e. the Management agenda) into their own quality worlds. In schools, therefore when learners agree to customize their quality worlds in this way, they called do quality works and in the process transition.

Disciplinary Tips in Schools.

1. **Help Students Stay More Focused on their Goals:** Discipline in the classroom held students stay focused on their academic over time, the teacher's then how to focus in other ways of learning. A disciplined student is able to stay focused on the goals and keep his work a top priority. This focus translates well into life outside this school, help students maintain high standard in every areas of life. A well-disciplined student stay focused on the moral ethics of the school and keep the community school relationship for better improvement of the education standard of the society which will increase national productivity at the end of the child education and become a greater benefit to the society at large.
2. **Limit Problem with Negative Peer Pressure:** Peer pressure can be both positive and negative factor in a student's life but having discipline in school can help limit the amount of negative peer pressure student face. Students are less likely to push their peers to make negative choices, when the entire student body is held to a high standard. As a result, peer pressure that does occur in the accountability to do and be better.
3. **Creates a Safe Environment for Students:** School discipline is the safety which is created in the school by the school authority. This is particularly true in boarding schools' environment where student live and learn in the same palace. When an established discipline code is in place, that students and teachers both understand and accept the rules. Everyone can learn in a safe and supportive environment for effective teaching and learning to flow into the student mind.

Types of Disciplinary Measures in Schools

Anggraeni (2020) identified three disciplinary measures such as preventive measures, supportive measures and corrective measures.

- i. **Preventive Disciplinary Measure:** Preventive disciplinary measures are strategies to avert misconduct in learning environment. Fasasi, Sakiyo and Jibasen (2022) noted that preventive measures are always used on students before the behaviour becomes a major issue. Luwumba, Lyamtane and Muteti (2022) asserted that in preventive measures, school administrators and teachers establish guideline and rules for students to follow in schools in order to reduce indiscipline cases by explaining to students what behaviors are and not acceptable in school and emphasize good manners, and respect for all individuals in the school environment.
- ii. **Supportive Disciplinary Measure:** It involves rendering assistance and guidance to students to regulate their behaviour. Luwumba et al (2022) pointed out that supportive discipline measures a teacher offers a verbal warning like eye contact, head shaking or a suggestion for correcting behavior while a student is disobeying an established school rules. Furthermore, they stressed that supportive discipline measures provide a student with suggestion and options for correction behavior before punishing students.
- iii. **Corrective Disciplinary Measure:** It involves taking actions against individuals that violate rules and regulations. It entails the use of punishment, warning, suspension and expulsion to remedy misconduct in learning institutions.

Best Practices for Maintaining Discipline in Schools

- i. **Increase Parental Involvement:** Parent truly make a difference in student's achievement and behavior. School should develop policy where teachers are required to contact parents periodically throughout the year. Half term often not enough. A parent cannot help solve an issue if they do not know one exists. While home calls take time, in the end they can help provide solutions to very difficult classroom problems. This is not to say that all parents' involvement will be positive or have a measurable effect on student's behavior. Nevertheless, this is an area which many successful school claim makes a huge difference than unsuccessful schools.
- ii. **Create and Enforce a School Wide Discipline Plan:** Discipline plans are a way to provide students with a consistent and fair plan of what will happen if they misbehave. While some schools have a discipline plan on book may do not have disciplinary plan on conduct/behavior. Having it posted in every classroom and in notice boards around the school premises/compound is a valid way to start controlling students.
- iii. **Practice Effective Following Through:** While posting the discipline plain it is important, so that all student is formed of the consequences for misbehavior. Following through of the discipline plan is the key to truly fostering discipline in school. In the classroom situation, if a teacher does not follow through the deal with misbehavior, it will increase school wide. If administrator do not follow the discipline plan and support the teachers, it would easily lose control of the situation.
- iv. **Foster Discipline in School Through Leadership:** The school administrator and assistant school administrator are very important keys in fostering discipline in any academically organization in focus school. Their actions form a basic of the overall mood for the students. If they are consistent in importing teacher's implementation the discipline plan and following through on disciplinary actions, then teachers will follow their lead. On the other hand, if they are lax on discipline, this will become apparent over time and misbehavior will increase in the school.
- v. **Build a Reputation for Fairness:** In hand with effective leadership and school wide consistent follow through is the belief by that teachers and administrators are fair in their discipline actions. While there are sometimes extenuating circumstance to make adjustments for individual students. Overall students whose misbehavior should be treated disciplinary. Teachers must act fairly for all students. If teacher do not threat all students equitably, they will be no respect, they will be labeled as unfair. Students will not be keen to follow their rules.
- vi. **Maintain High Expectation:** from administrator to guidance and counsellors to teachers, school must institute high expectations from both acknowledgment and behavior. This expectation must include message of encouragement and mean of support to help all children succeed.

According to Molntyre (2005) schools that foster high-esteem and promote social and scholastic success reduce the likelihood of emotional and behavior disturbance. Expect that students will behave not that they will disrupt. Teachers should reinforce this with the way they speak to their students, teacher should begin the day by telling students their expectation. For example, a teacher telling students that if you study well and pass examination with flying colours, you have opportunities of series of high pay job in the social and the society will have respect for you.

- vii. **Deal with Disruption with as Little Interruption as Possible:** When teacher have classroom disruptions, it is imperative that they deal with them immediately and with as little interruption of their classroom momentum as possible. If students are taking among themselves and the teacher is having a classroom discussion, ask one of them a question

to try and get them back on track. If the teacher has to stop the flow of his/her lesson to deal with disruption, then he/she is robbing students who want to learn of their precious in class time. Teachers should use their best judgment it realizes that what some people think as funny other time to be offensive.

Conclusion

Disciplinary problems are normal issues such as students' misbehavior attitudes, school dropout, students' violence attitudes, lateness to school and other negative social behaviours are sources of concern to educational stakeholders and the society. Disciple model or theory could help to improve the different ideas of handle disciples, such as Kounins model, centre's assertive behaviour model, cognitivist William Glasser's theories among others. All these models create impacts to school disciple for students' improvement. Also the types of disciple model in school could help teachers to handle disciplinary issues by controlling the behaviour of student. It encourages teacher-students' relationship to flow well in the school setting. The best means to maintain discipline in school is to foster more awareness of the school rules and regulation that govern the school environment, which can lead to better improvement of teaching-learning activities in the classroom.

Recommendations

The Following recommendations were made:

1. School administrators should encourage the formation of clubs and societies. Through participating in school activities, clubs and societies, students can gain a sense of togetherness and learn good moral value such as co-operation, honesty, leadership and independence, which will promote the character moulding of the students to obey society norms.
2. School administrators should encourage participation of students and parents in disciplinary matters. Through student and parents' participation in formulating school rules and regulation, they will become aware of school rules and possible punishments for violation.
3. School rules should be tightening and strictly enforced to curb bad behaviour in school. Any students caught committing serious offences such as vandalism, arson, extortion, fighting, stealing should be given severe warning and be part under surveillance.
4. Government should qualify guidance and counseling teachers in employed in all schools for help in handling disciplinary issues in school.
5. School administrator should encourage teachers to attend current conferences, seminar and workshop for better improvement of their knowledge in controlling students' behaviour in the classroom.
6. The teacher and school administrator should encourage and reward good behave students on daily bases. It will boost the moral accept of the student especially the reward will be on morning assemble.

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